

Punch the Monkey and the Plush Imago:

Reflecting on Heinz Kohut's 'The Analysis of the Self.'

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Abstract

This essay uses the viral story of Punch, a baby Japanese macaque abandoned by his mother at Japan's Ichikawa City Zoo, to explore key concepts from Heinz Kohut's *The Analysis of the Self* (1971/2009). By examining Punch's attachment to a surrogate stuffed orangutan provided by zookeepers, the author illustrates Kohut's concepts of the Idealized Parent Imago, selfobject function, and transmuting internalization. The essay considers how Punch's gradual relinquishment of the surrogate mirrors healthy developmental processes, and what Kohut's framework reveals about narcissistic personality organization when those processes fail in human development.

Keywords: Heinz Kohut, self psychology, Idealized Parent Imago, selfobject, transmuting internalization, narcissistic personality organization, Punch the Monkey, psychoanalysis, developmental psychology, surrogate attachment

If you've spent any amount of time on social media the past few weeks, you've likely come across viral videos of an adorable baby monkey named Punch, who had been abandoned by his mother shortly after birth in a Japanese zoo. In ethological terms, this is a catastrophic event; an infant primate stripped of maternal regulation is left entirely exposed to the chaotic, terrifying stimuli of the environment. But what makes this story so cool is that, to ensure his survival, zookeepers ingeniously provided Punch with an unconventional surrogate mother: a stuffed orange orangutan doll from IKEA. Yep. IKEA. The visual of Punch, a tiny, hyper-vigilant monkey desperately burying his face into the plush, synthetic fur of a lifeless stuffed animal when rejected by the older monkeys of his troop, is undeniably poignant. Coincidentally, as Punch's videos began going viral, I had just started reading 'The Analysis of the Self' by Heinz Kohut. A colleague had recommended it to me for thinking through the treatment of some of my more complicated patients. Needless to say, I had much of Kohut's dense writing and abstract theorizing on my mind while perusing X, Reddit, and everywhere else Punch kept turning up. Sure enough, as if compelled by unconscious forces, I found myself conceptualizing Punch's relationship with his surrogate plush parent in a way that helped me understand some of Kohut's more abstract concepts, specifically the Idealized Parent Imago, selfobject need, and transmuting internalization.

Let's first unpack what Kohut actually means by "The Parent Imago" because he can be loquacious and hard to follow. So despite the implications of the word "imago" (Latin for image), Kohut isn't literally referring to a frozen mental image of a parental figure in the individual's memory. What Kohut is referring to is the unconscious, deeply subjective, and often idealized mental prototype of a significant figure from childhood, usually a parent or caregiver. It's not an objective memory of who your parent actually was, but an almost mythic representation of what the parent felt like to the infant. In Kohut's view, this reflects an innate developmental hunger for an omnipotent, perfect caretaker; a need felt by all infants that can remain frozen when development is disrupted.

In Punch's case, that developmental process was disrupted almost immediately when his mother abandoned him, depriving him of the safety, regulation, and bodily reassurance that infant primates depend on for survival. Compounding this situation was the harsh rejection Punch experienced from the other macaques in the zoo's troop, as well as the aggression and even bullying he endured at the hands of some of the older monkeys. These compounding ruptures created an unsafe environment of instability at precisely the moment when he should have been developing within a secure maternal and social holding environment. Yet despite the absence of a primary caregiver, the little primate's innate drive to find an all-powerful, soothing figure remained.

Enter the quick-thinking zookeepers at the Ichikawa City Zoo, who recognized Punch's need for comfort and security. When zookeepers introduced the stuffed orangutan (affectionately dubbed "Oramama" by the internet), Punch appears to have immediately projected that Idealized Parent Imago onto it, latching onto it in times of need. Indeed, many of the original viral videos are of Punch running to the plush monkey doll and holding onto it for safety after being rejected by the other macaques. For Punch, that toy is not merely a plaything, but a piece of his own psychological machinery; what Kohut somewhat unintuitively conceptualizes as the "selfobject." Kohut posits that to small infants, the world is terrifying and chaotic, and to survive this terror, infants project absolute omnipotence, omniscience, and perfect calm onto their caretakers. In Kohut's view, infants need their caregiver to be a literal god. In human terms, this means that even a stressed-out and exhausted single mom working 40 hours a week and who, like all humans, is fallible, is idealized by the infant as an all-soothing force of nature. This idealization enables the infant to survive by mentally "merging" as one, or merging the self (the infant) with the object (the caregiver). In Punch's case, it doesn't matter that his maternal figure is nothing more than a lifeless plush doll. It was "good enough" (Winnicott, 1971), and he projected the idealized image onto it, as we can see in those original viral videos of him clinging tightly to the plush doll after being bullied, in order to prevent what Kohut calls fragmentation.

Kohut writes that when a caregiver is “good enough,” and as the infant enters childhood, they will begin to realize the caregiver was never all-perfect nor omnipotent. This experience, which Kohut names “Transmuting Internalization,” results in the Idealized Parent Imago gradually being dismantled, yet the child has strong enough ego-strength to develop their own ability to self-soothe. In more recent updates from the zoo, we have seen new videos where Punch is finally starting to be groomed by the adult macaques. As he slowly gains acceptance, visitors have noticed him occasionally leaving the plushie on the other side of the enclosure while he plays or interacts with the troop. When viewed through this Kohutian lens, we are literally watching transmuting internalization happen. Because the zookeepers didn't prematurely strip away his surrogate, because they allowed him to use it to regulate himself and project the Parent Imago onto it, the reliable, external soothing of the self-object is giving him enough baseline security to slowly build his own internal resilience and enter the social world.

Interestingly, the core point of Kohut's book, and why I read it, is for the treatment of Narcissistically Organized individuals. What I have described above in Punch, due to the successful implementation of a surrogate mother, is a healthy developmental process that most often prevents the infant from developing a pathological narcissistic organization. In Punch's case, the plush was “good enough” to serve the infant's needs. However, with humans, ironically, another species of primate who, in many ways, are not too different from Punch, a stuffed animal in place of a human caregiver would likely not have been enough for the child to project the Idealized Parent Imago onto it. Kohut describes that, in these more traumatic situations, the developing psyche is threatened with catastrophic fragmentation, and the child can never dismantle the Imago. Moreover, he argues that the child cannot achieve transmuting internalization, leaving their narcissistic needs frozen in an archaic state. Kohut posits that, as adults, these individuals will wander the world desperately looking for someone to project this Idealized Parent Imago onto -- a guru, a perfect romantic partner, or a therapist -- so they can finally merge with it and feel safe. As I stated earlier, Kohut's writing is dense and can be difficult to

parse out. Indeed, at times I felt as if I were being hit in the head with the book in lieu of absorbing the material. However, reading Kohut through Punch, while also thinking of some of my own clients, made his ideas feel much more tangible to me. It helped me see why treatment would require not simply confronting narcissistic defenses head-on, but allowing the patient's unmet developmental needs to emerge within the therapeutic relationship so that something like transmuting internalization can finally occur. So, in other words, with some of these more narcissistically organized individuals who come into therapy, maybe it's the therapists who were the plushies all along.

This essay also served as the basis for a companion video essay:

Punch the Monkey | Psychotherapist Explains Heinz Kohut's Psychoanalysis

<https://youtu.be/T4nYns9Xwf8>

References

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